

Standard Operating Procedure	Version: 2
Identification of ESBL <i>K. pneumoniae</i> using melt curve PCR.	
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Version History

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	01/04/19	Initial version
2.0	01/08/19	Changes after initial pilot phase

1. Introduction

This method is applicable for the identification of ESBL *K. pneumoniae* (ESBL-K) from samples cultured on chromogenic agar, obtained from households included in the DRUM study.

The proportion of patients admitted to hospitals in Uganda and Malawi with invasive infections caused by ESBL resistant Enterobacteriaceae including ESBL-E and ESBL-K is increasing. Given the reduced availability of Carbapenems, many of these drug-resistant infections are locally untreatable. To understand the drivers of this antimicrobial resistance, further evidence of the role of household environment contamination on human and animal carriage with ESBL-E and ESBL-K is required.

2. Purpose

Melt-curve PCR will be used to identify *K. pneumoniae* isolates cultured on chromogenic agar.

3. Responsibilities

- Field workers
 - Collection of human and animal stool, and environmental samples in accordance with Sample Collection SOPs
 - Correct labelling of collection samples
 - Prompt transport of collected samples to the laboratory
 - Completion of sample collection log
- Study Laboratory Technicians
 - Register samples on DRUM teleform / eLIMS system
 - Double-check correct sample labelling
 - Processing ESBL positive samples in accordance with this SOP
 - Storage of samples for further analysis in accordance with this SOP
- Principal Investigators
 - Ensure laboratory training in sample processing procedures provided
 - Undertake quality control checks of laboratory processing.

4. Procedure

4.1 Materials and Equipment needed

Sterile 10ul Bacterial loops

Microbank storage vial with beads

Qiagen Type-it HRM PCR Kit

Molecular Grade Water

0.2ml PCR Tube, Flat Cap, 0.2ml 96 well PCR plates

Conical centrifuge tubes

Primer Mix (see below)

Heat block

Microcentrifuge tubes

Vortex Mixer

Micro-centrifuge

Pipettes, precision

Stopwatch

Gloves

PCR labcoats

4.2 Storage conditions

All reagents should be stored as per the instructions of the manufacturer

4.3. Test Procedure – Sample selection and storage

1. Read chromogenic agar plate after 18-24 hours. ANY growth is a potential ESBL producer.
2. For colonies that are typical for *K. pneumoniae* (see below), confirm speciation with HRM PCR.

Appearance*	Organism*
Metallic blue (+/- reddish halo) 	ESBL KEC (Klebsiella, Enterobacter, Citrobacter)

* Pictures and organism ID taken from CHROMAgar™ ESBL NT-EXT-034 V5.0 / 08-Aug-16

3. Once a suitable colony is identified, take a small loop of part of the colony and DNA extract / run PCR (4.3 / 4.4/ Appendix 1).
4. Store the rest of the (same) colony in a microbank vial at -80°C and complete the DRUM teleforms indicating the PCR result for *K. pneumoniae*.

4.3 Test Procedure – Boilate DNA Extraction (Also covered in Appendix 1)

If extracting DNA directly from bacterial colony:

1. Dispense 200µl Molecular Biology Grade Water into Microcentrifuge tube
2. Resuspend a single colony of bacteria in the water
3. Vortex for 15s
4. Briefly spin down to collect the liquid in the bottom of the tube
5. Heat tube at 95°C for 10 minutes
6. Vortex for 15s
7. Centrifuge at 8000rpm for 5 minutes to pellet cell debris
8. Transfer supernatant to a fresh centrifuge tube (or well of a 96 well plate) and dilute 1:50 in molecular grade water
9. Store at -20°C until required or continue to PCR

If freezing bacterial colony to extract DNA at later date:

1. Dispense 200µl Molecular Biology Grade Water into Microcentrifuge tube
2. Resuspend a single colony of bacteria in the water
3. Freeze at -80°C
4. When required for PCR, defrost and follow procedure from Step 5 above.

4.4 Test Procedure - PCR

Procedure requires qPCR system capable of melt analysis with 0.1C melt rate
Use Quantstudio 7k or Rotorgene

Method

Set up 12.5ul PCR reactions up as per **Appendix 1**

1. Carry out PCR with the following conditions:
2. Hold 95C, 5 mins
3. 30x cycles of 95C 10 secs, 58C 30 secs, 72C 10 secs
4. Acquire on FAM (green) channel during 72C step
5. Melt from 75C to 92C, rising 0.1C each step (important), 90 secs pre-melt conditioning on first step, 2 secs per each step afterwards, data collection in FAM/HRM
6. Include a positive control *K. pneumoniae* and a negative control (Molecular grade water) in each run.
7. PCR results for *K. pneumoniae* should be written on the DRUM teleform system.

5. Quality Control

Quality control will be tested with known ESBL producing organisms (both in house and commercially available)

6. Health and Safety

Please refer to risk assessment tools and local health and safety guidelines

Appendix 1

Klebsiella primers working solution:

1. Take a **clean 1.5ml Eppendorf tube** and **label 'Kleb'** with **today's date**.
2. Pipette **80 µl** of **sterile water**.
3. Pipette **10µl** of **forward primer** and add to tube.
4. Pipette **10µl** of **reverse primer** and add to tube.
5. **Vortex** for 10 seconds.

Store in the clean room freezer.

Master mix preparation

Take the **working solution** of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* primers, **the HRM type IT mix** and the molecular grade water from the **clean room freezer**.

- **Label a clean Eppendorf tube** with '**MM**' and the **date**.
- Prepare master mix working solution as shown in the table below
- It is good to make up enough mix for 100 reactions, so we can store and use quickly next time.

Component	x1	x100
HRM IT mix	6.25	625
Kleb working solution	0.5	50
H ₂ O	3.25	325
Total	10µl	100µl

Preparing the plates/tubes for reaction

1. Remove the **plate cold block** from the **clean room freezer**.
2. If **using tubes**, take the **blue QuantStudio bottom tube holder** and place on top of the cold block and then **add the rows of tubes**. If **using plate**, place the plate on top of the cold block.
3. Pipette **10µl** of the **master mix** to each well.

For negative control, it is advised to add 2.5ul of molecular water into designated negative control well/tube in the clean room since the negative control is molecular water and is clean.

Move into the **DNA loading room** now.

Loading DNA

1. Pipette **2.5µl** of **DNA** into each well.
2. Pipette 2.5ul of positive control into a designated well/tube for positive control
3. Cover the tubes/seal the wells

Running Melt curve PCR

1. If using Quant Studio, centrifuge the plate/strips at 1000rpm for 1 minute before loading into the Quantstudio machine. Match the A1 orientation of the sample plate/strips with that of the plate/strip holder. No need to centrifuge if using Rotorgene.
2. Create and use a template for melt curve PCR with properties that have been provided above
3. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* melts between 80-82⁰c on the melt curve
4. *After qPCR run, discard the plate/strip/tubes in a designated bin to avoid contamination of the machine room with amplicons.*